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Impact of a lightweight generator on tower design and control optimization of a floating wind turbine

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Abstract. The present study investigates the structural and dynamic implications of integrating a novel lightweight generator technology into modern FOWTs. The investigated generator design has recently been patented by the Swedish start-up Hagnesia and is able to achieve up to a tenfold reduction in generator mass compared with conventional designs. Changes in system performance are analyzed by (i) quantifying variations in structural loads, (ii) exploring the potential for tower redesign, and (iii) assessing whether further load mitigation can be achieved through control co-design (CCD). All configurations are analyzed under two different metocean conditions representative of the western coast of Barra Island (Scotland) and another of offshore Sicily (Italy), respectively, thus enabling a sensitivity study to site-specific metocean characteristics. Results indicate that mean structural loads in the substructure, such as the tower-base bending moment in the fore-aft direction, can be reduced relative to the benchmark configuration (i.e., the state-of-the-art generator of the IEA 15MW rotor), but maximum values may instead be higher. CCD of the floating substructure can mitigate these effects by minimizing the fore-aft tower-base bending moment Damage Equivalent Load. The mechanisms leading to the observed behavior are broken-down and discussed in detail, linking the impact of nacelle weight to FOWT design and performance.

1. Introduction

As floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) scale to higher capacities and larger sizes, the Rotor Nacelle Assembly (RNA) becomes heavier and is cantilevered progressively higher above sea level. In fact, increases in tower height make the associated pitching moments become more significant, as they contribute to the inertial and gravitational loads acting on the turbine substructure when the system tilts and moves under external aerodynamic and hydrodynamic forces. In this perspective, RNA's mass is becoming increasingly important in modern wind turbine design. To address this issue, the Swedish startup Hagnesia has developed the Poloidal or Tangential Flux technology [1], which is specifically designed for low-speed direct-drive applications. The main characteristics of this technology include a significant mass reduction of approximately 90% at the MW scale, resulting in a generator mass of about 30 tons for a 15MW rated power, which is substantially lower than that of existing direct-drive generators, whose mass typically ranges between 300 tons for a 15MW machine to 500 tons for a 22MW one [2], [3]. The technological shift affects both active and structural materials, as well as generator efficiency, which can reach up to 98%. As a consequence of the substantial reduction in raw material usage, this technology also enhances sustainability from economic, environmental, and social perspectives, while reducing dependence on the supply of critical raw materials. The present study addresses the potential impact that this reduction in generator weight can have on

the loads and structural requirements of the wind turbine at different levels. In fact, a reduction in generator mass, cantilevered at the tower top, leads - as discussed - to reduced inertial and gravitational loading when the turbine responds to external excitations. This can result in reduced structural demand on the tower, thus paving the way to a redesign of this component. In addition to the tower, the reduction in the RNA mass also affects the substructure and the dynamic behavior of the entire system. It should be noted that in FOWTs the dynamic behavior of the individual subsystems (such as substructure, rotor, tower, controller, etc.) is highly coupled. Consequently, integrating system dynamics into the design process through Control Co-Design (CCD), rather than optimizing single components sequentially, can reduce structural loads and improve the overall performance of the wind turbine system [4][5]. In this study the reference open-source IEA 15MW Reference Wind Turbine [2] in its floating configuration with the VoltturnUS-S semisubmersible platform is considered. The baseline generator is first drop-in replaced with the corresponding lightweight generator by Hagnesia. Then, the feasibility of tower redesign is explored, and the floating platform and controller are co-optimized. To evaluate the sensitivity of the resulting tower and platform designs under different external loading conditions the endeavor was repeated in two different offshore sites. The first site is characterized by relatively mild wind and wave conditions and is located offshore of the western coast of Sicily, Italy. The second site corresponds to the metocean conditions west of Barra Island, Scotland. The study is organized as follows. First, an overview of the optimization methods is provided, detailing how the optimizations themselves are defined and which tools are used, together with a discussion of the modelling choices and the adopted metocean conditions. Results are then presented and discussed in Section 3, highlighting the main benefits as well as the principal challenges encountered when applying this novel lightweight generator technology.

2. Methods

All phases of this study, including loads evaluation, tower optimization, and the coupled control-co-design have been performed through the QBtoWEIS framework [6], through which the Wind Energy and Integrated Servo Controls optimization toolbox (WEIS [7]) and the non-linear time domain simulator QBlade [8] are coupled. These two pieces of software have been coupled within Work Package 7 of the EU-funded project "FLOATFARM" to enable multi fidelity co-design [9]. QBtoWEIS enables multi-fidelity analyses by allowing for the selection of different modeling schemes for each task at hand, including frequency-domain tools such as Response Amplitudes of Floating Turbines (RAFT [10]), and fully nonlinear OpenFAST and QBlade solvers. For optimization and load analysis in this study, WISDEM and QBlade are used. Different objective functions are considered for the tower optimization and for the coupled floater-controller optimization, as detailed in the following sections. Four wind turbine configurations were optimized and are denoted using the naming convention [site]-[TOPT]-[LWG]. [site] identifies the metocean conditions (B for Barra and S for Sicily), [TOPT] indicates that the tower of the IEA 15 MW RWT was optimized for the selected site, and [LWG] denotes configurations equipped with the lightweight generator. All configurations make use of the IEA 15 MW RWT rotor and start from its baseline design.

2.1 Tower optimization

Tower optimization is carried out within WEIS by leveraging the underlying OpenMDAO framework [11], using WISDEM as the steady state model solver for FOWTs. For the calculation of the rigid body natural periods, RAFT [10] is used. RAFT provides a linear representation of the

FOWT and can compute response amplitude operators resulting from disturbances, which can be modelled in the frequency domain (such as wind turbulence and wave spectra) over a discrete set of frequencies, as well as system eigenfrequencies and hydrostatic properties. For the tower optimization in this study, the lowest frequency was set to 0.002 Hz, and the highest frequency was set to 0.6 Hz. Hydrodynamics are modelled using strip theory (Morison's equation) with a drag coefficient of 0.8 and an added-mass coefficient of 1.0. WISDEM was chosen over QBlade for the optimization process because it is much faster and significantly reduces the computational cost compared with a nonlinear time-domain solver while maintaining sufficient accuracy for conceptual-level tower design. The main loads considered for the analysis are the steady-state aerodynamic loads computed by CCBlade [12], the hydrodynamic pseudo-static loads computed with the Morison's equation, and gravity loads. WISDEM approximates extreme aerodynamic loading using an equivalent gust defined as $U = \bar{U} + n\sigma$, where $\sigma = TI \cdot \bar{U}$. While the default value is $n = 3$, this study uses $n = 5$ to conservatively increase the estimated aerodynamic loads, thereby also accounting for the additional loads induced by the FOWTs motion. The tower optimization was performed in DLC 1.6 under both Barra and Sicily metocean conditions, and the tower was discretized by 11 points along its length. The design variables for tower optimization are the tower diameter and the wall thickness along the tower height; all variables are subject to lower and upper bounds as reported in Table 1. The optimization minimizes the tower mass subjected to constraints on the first natural frequency of the tower, whose lower bound is set to be at least 25% above the 3P frequency. Other constraints are set on the taper ratio, with both quantities constrained within prescribed lower and upper limits. Buckling constraints and stress constraints [13] are also active to ensure that structurally-sound designs are generated.

Table 1. Design variables and constraints for tower and substructure optimizations.

	Constraints	Lower bound	Upper bound	Design Var.	Lower bound	Upper bound
Tower	f_1 [Hz]	0.473	0.55	D [m]	6.5	10
	taper [-]	0.5	-	thickness [m]	0.004	0.10
Control Co-Design	nac. acc. [m/s]	-	2.0	ω_{pc} [Hz]	0.025	0.50
	ptfm pitch [°]	-	6.0	ζ_{pc} [-]	0.5	2.5
	rot. overspeed [-]	-	0.20	k_{float} [-]	-14	-6
	pitch travel [°/s]	-	0.085	ω_{ptfm} [Hz]	0.00001	0.5
	ptfm mass [kg]	-	initial value	col. diam. [m]	10	15
	AEP [GWh/y]	initial value	-	draft [m]	-25	-15
	pitch period [s]	22	40	col. spacing [m]	45	60

2.2 Load analysis

QBlade is used for loads' evaluation. As in tower optimization, WEIS serves as the top-level framework, while the specific dynamic solver is the nonlinear time-domain code QBlade. In this analysis, the floater geometry and its dynamic properties are fixed. The hydrodynamic behavior of the floater is modeled by representing viscous drag through strip theory, based on the hydrodynamic coefficients described in [4]. The frequency-dependent added-mass and damping coefficients are evaluated using a boundary-element method through the frequency-domain solver HAMS [14], coupled with RAFT via PyHAMS [15]. Furthermore, the platform is meshed using panels of 2×2 m. The wave field in QBlade is modelled using a JONSWAP spectrum. Equal-energy discretization is used herein to discretize the wave spectrum, and 10000 frequency bins are used. Aerodynamics are modelled using the unsteady Blade Element Momentum (BEM) formulation [16], which allows one to account for the azimuthal variation of the induction factor.

In turn, this allows for the modelling of phenomena such as the atmospheric boundary layer, turbulence, and other unsteady disturbances. Structural dynamics are based on the Finite Element Analysis module of the open source multi-physics engine Project Chrono [17], which enables a structural modelling of the wind turbine as a multi body system, in which both the blades and the tower are modelled with the Euler-Bernoulli beam formulation. Aerodynamics are then coupled with structural dynamics with a loose coupling approach [8]. QBlade was also used to assess that all the tower designs obtained through the procedure described in Section 2.1 are structurally sound and that buckling and stress constraints are satisfied. In fact, the time-domain approach removes the simplifications inherent in steady-state or frequency domain tools. To do so, DLC 1.6 was analyzed.

2.3 Control co-design

An optimization of the floater and controller is carried out in the same four cases specified in the tower optimization section. Since the IEA 15MW RWT is the selected benchmark FOWT, the starting platform and controller are the baseline semisubmersible VoltornUS-S platform [2] and the reference Open-Source Controller (ROSCO [18]). The VoltornUS-S platform is a semi-submersible composed of a main center column supporting the wind turbine and three external columns which are connected through cylindrical pontoons. ROSCO is a modular, open-source controller, and it was designed to replicate the functionality of standard industry controllers. ROSCO is also provided with a floating offshore wind turbine feedback module, which helps to stabilize the platform motion by adding damping to the platform itself and avoiding the negative-damping problem [19][20]. In the present analysis, focus is given to the optimization of main collective pitch-to-feather controller parameters as shown in Table 1. The design variables of this optimization process are the floating feedback gain k_{float} , the floating feedback filter cutoff frequency ω_{ptfm} , the natural frequency of the pitch controller ω_{pc} and the damping ratio of the pitch controller ζ_{pc} . The latter (ω_{pc} and ζ_{pc}) are scheduled on three different values of the wind speed: 12, 17, 23 m/s. Floater design variables include the platform radius, draft, and semi-submersible column diameter. All these values influence both the static and dynamic response of the platform. All design variables and constraints are summarized in Table 1. The AEP is constrained not to decrease with respect to its initial value, and the platform mass is constrained not to increase, while all the wall thickness of all components is kept constant as no structural assessment on them is performed. Constraints on ballast are imposed also imposed in the simulations: the floater design should provide sufficient volume to hold the specified fixed ballast and variable water ballast to achieve neutral buoyancy. The rigid-body motion natural frequencies of the FOWT system must remain below the lower-frequency bound of the wave spectrum in order to avoid resonance.

WEIS serves as the top-level framework for the coupled controller-floater optimization, while QBlade is used to perform time-domain simulations. As the floater geometry is continuously changing during the optimizations, the hydrodynamic characteristics of the floater are recomputed at each iteration with PyHams. The wave field is discretized in 10000 equal frequency spacing linear wave components.

2.4 Metocean conditions and Design Load Cases

Two sets of metocean conditions are considered: a harsher site, located west of the Isle of Barra (Scotland) [21], characterized by high wind speeds and severe sea states, and a milder site, off the coast of Sicily (Italy) [22] with lower wind speeds and reduced significant wave heights. For load analysis, DLC 1.1 [23] was used, representative of normal operating conditions, with

wind speeds from 3 m/s to 25 m/s in 2 m/s increments. Four turbulent seeds are considered for each wind speed. Each simulation was run for a total duration of 1250 s and to reduce the influence of transients, the initial 250 s were discarded, resulting in a total simulated time of one hour and a half for each mean wind speed. For the aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulations performed in CCD phase, DLC 1.1 was also used as well as a total simulation time of 1250 s, with a 250 s transient period and four turbulent seeds were selected for each mean wind speed.

3. Results

3.1 Tower optimization

Results from the tower optimization are summarized in Fig. 1. Even when using the reference generator, the optimizer is able to reduce tower mass with respect to the reference turbine. The first natural frequency converges to 0.473 Hz for both the TOPT and TOPT-LWG towers (Tab. 2), which is equal to the lower bound imposed in the optimization, indicating that natural frequency is a design-driving constraint. When redesigning towers in FOWTs, the primary design-driving parameter is the maximum thrust, as also discussed in [24]. The thrust force does not vary significantly between configurations, since the rotor is identical in all cases. However, a mass reduction of up to -11% in the TOPT configuration and up to -25% in the TOPT-LWG configuration compared to the reference IEA 15MW RWT is achieved. If we compare the TOPT configuration with the TOPT-LWG, a -16% mass reduction in tower was achieved. A reduction in RNA weight, which is cantilevered hundreds of meters above the sea surface, causes an increase in natural frequency, which is exploited by the optimizer to reduce mass. Furthermore, identical designs are obtained when using the Barra and Sicily met-ocean conditions, as shown in Fig. 1, confirming that the designs are not buckling or load constrained. The results shown in Fig. 1 ultimately demonstrate that significant mass and raw material savings can be unlocked by reducing the first natural frequency of the floating tower and additional mass reduction is obtained when a lighter RNA is adopted.

Figure 1. Results of tower optimization in the four analyzed configuration of the IEA 15MW RWT.

Table 2 Main parameters of the redesigned turbine towers. Configuration with the optimized tower only (TOPT); configuration with the lightweight generator and optimized tower (TOPT-LWG); reference turbine (REF). No distinction is made between the Barra and Sicily sites, as the resulting tower design is identical in both conditions. f_1 is the first natural frequency of the floating tower, f_{1_tower} is the first natural frequency of the fixed tower.

	TOPT	TOPT-LWG	REF
Gen mass [t]	368.839	30	368.839
RNA mass [t]	959.533	608.942	959.533
Tower mass [t]	1317.398	1102.522	1483.075
f_1 [Hz]	0.473	0.473	0.524
f_{1_tower} [Hz]	0.3375	0.3645	0.3756

Figure 2. Global buckling (a), shell buckling (b), and stress (c) utilization checks for the optimized tower as a function of normalized tower length. Results computed with time domain solver and computed using distributed loads corresponding to maximum tower base fore-aft bending moment in DLC 1.6.

A structural assessment of the final tower designs was then performed in QBlade, following the procedure described in Section 2.2. To this end, each tower was discretized into 30 sections. The final designs were assessed under DLC 1.6. The local loads that generate the maximum fore-aft bending moment in this DLC are used for the ultimate stress and buckling limits check. Figure 2 summarizes the outcome of this assessment in terms of global buckling (Fig. 2a), shell buckling (Fig. 2b), and stress (Fig. 2c) for all the four configurations. The B-TOPT-LWG configuration nearly reaches the global limit on buckling, particularly at tower’s section 4, while it is still able to respect the constraint. Overall, all configurations satisfy structural requirements, confirming their feasibility also under the nonlinear time-domain analysis.

Figure 3. Mean values (solid, dashed and dotted lines), maximum values (triangles) and minimum values (reversed triangles) as a function of mean wind speed of the aerodynamic power (a,f), aerodynamic thrust (b,g), platform pitch (c,h), tower base fore-aft bending moment (d,i) and nacelle fore-aft acceleration (e,j). In the top row results from Barra metocean conditions, in the bottom row results from Sicily in DLC 1.1 simulations.

Figure 3 presents the statistics of the aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulations performed in QBlade for DLC 1.1. The first row reports the results for the Barra site, whereas the second row shows those for the Sicily site. As can also be observed with the help of Fig. 4, which reports the ratio of the overall maximums of the mean maxima within each wind-speed bin for each configuration with the IEA15MW RWT (Fig. 4(a)) and with the corresponding TOPT configurations (Fig. 4(b)), a clear trend can be identified in these simulations: reducing the natural frequency of the floating tower with respect to the benchmark turbine (Fig. 4(a)) leads in all configurations to slightly higher maximum values of the mean maxima for tower-top deflection in the x direction which increases in all configurations. Multiple root causes can be individuated. The tower is less rigid

than that of the benchmark turbine. Moreover, the reduced RNA mass in the TOPT-LWG configurations results in a lower rotational inertia about the rotation in y-direction. On the other hand, mean platform pitch is lower in the TOPT-LWG cases. Figure 4b further highlights the benefits associated with the adoption of the lightweight generator. Compared with the corresponding TOPT configurations, the TOPT-LWG solutions combine a lighter tower, achieved through tower optimization, with a lighter RNA, resulting in reduced tower-base fore-aft bending moment up to a maximum of -13% and lower platform pitch loads respect to TOPT designs up to a maximum of -17%. On the other hand, the lower tower stiffness leads to a slight increase in tower-top deflection in the TOPT-LWG configurations, whereas the nacelle acceleration in the x-direction becomes significantly higher due to the reduced inertia along the same direction. Modifying the dynamic properties of the system by reducing the RNA and tower masses provides several benefits in terms of raw material usage. However, this approach may introduce challenges in reducing maximum load values and displacements at the tower top, while potentially increasing the amplitudes of load fluctuations. For these reasons, a coupled optimization of the floater and the controller is considered in order to assess whether a reduction in DELs at the tower base bending moment in y-direction can be achieved.

Figure 4. Ratio of maximum values of the mean maxima within each wind-speed bin of the main parameters for the four analyzed configurations. Results are normalized by the reference turbine RWT (a) and by the TOPT configuration (b). All channels are evaluated in DLC 1.1.

3.2 CCD results

In the following analysis, the control co-design optimized configurations are denoted as [site]-CCD-TOPT-LWG for the cases featuring the optimized tower and the lightweight generator, and as [site]-CCD-TOPT for the cases featuring the optimized tower and the original RNA. Figure 5 presents the results of the CCD analysis for several key parameters across the four configurations. In Fig. 5(a), the percentage differences of selected key parameters between the optimized configuration and the starting configuration (i.e., last iteration point versus the first iteration point of CCD optimization) are reported. Figure 5(b) shows the percentage differences of the same key parameters between the CCD-optimized configurations and the IEA 15-MW RWT under analogous metocean conditions. A similar comparison, now between the CCD-TOPT-LWG and the CCD-TOPT configurations, is shown in Fig. 5(c). In all configurations, the optimization successfully reduces the initial value of the DEL. Under Sicily metocean conditions, the reduction in DEL achieved through the CCD is approximately -2% for the S-CCD-TOPT-LWG configuration and about -8% for the S-TOPT configuration. Under Barra conditions DEL decrease reaches -7% for the B-TOPT configuration and -4% for the B-CCD-TOPT-LWG configuration with respect to the initial values before the CCD optimization: here the coupled optimization of the controller and the floater appear to be more effective. A consistent trend is observed for the CCD-TOPT-LWG systems under both Barra and Sicily metocean conditions. The reduction in DEL is primarily associated with a decrease in Maximum Nacelle Acceleration (MNA in Fig. 5(a)) and a simultaneous increase

in Maximum Platform Pitch (MPP in Fig. 5(a)). This response is linked to more slender floating platforms, characterized by reduced column diameters and lower hydrostatic stiffness due to the smaller platform radius. As a result, the platform may experience lower wave induced excitation which reduces the nacelle acceleration in x-direction. The B-CCD-TOPT configuration follows a similar trend. In this case the reduction in platform radius is less pronounced but the overall behavior remains consistent with that observed for the CCD-TOPT-LWG configurations, where DEL reduction is achieved through a decrease in MNA.

Figure 5. (a) percentage difference between the initial design point and the final optimized design point obtained through CCD optimization, (b) percentage difference between optimized cases and RWT in same metocean conditions, (c) percentage difference between CCD-TOPT-LWG and CCD-TOPT optimized configurations in analogous metocean conditions. DEL denotes the damage-equivalent fore-aft tower-base bending moment. MNA denotes the maximum nacelle acceleration in the x-direction, MPP the maximum platform pitch, Ptfm. mass the platform mass, Radius the platform radius, Draft the platform draft, and Diameter the platform column diameter.

Different trends are observed in the CCD-S-TOPT configuration. In this case, the platform draft is significantly reduced compared to the original design, while the optimizer increases both the column diameter and the platform radius, which may lead to higher wave induced excitation. This is reflected in a decrease in MPP at the expense of an increase in MNA. This configuration emerges under milder metocean conditions, as the optimizer achieves a reduction in DEL through a different strategy from the one adopted in CCD-TOPT-LWG configurations. Figure 5(b) illustrates the overall effect of combining tower redesign with controller co-design in the CCD-TOPT configurations, as well as the additional replacement of the baseline generator with the Hagnesia lightweight generator in the CCD-TOPT-LWG configurations. The beneficial impact of these combined optimization steps is particularly evident in the DEL, which is substantially reduced relative to the RWT under the same site-specific metocean conditions, up to a maximum of -16%. The improvement becomes even more pronounced when the CCD-TOPT-LWG configurations are compared with the corresponding CCD-TOPT cases in Fig 5(c), indicating that the introduction of the lightweight generator, together with tower optimization and controller-floater co-design, provides a significant benefit in terms of DEL. It is also worth noting that the maximum nacelle acceleration is reduced relative to the RWT only in the CCD-B-TOPT configuration. This trend is consistent with the lower radius of the CCD-B-TOPT platform discussed above, for which the combined effect of a more compliant pitch response and the higher RNA mass and inertia, relative

to the LWG case, appears to reduce the acceleration of the nacelle. In contrast, the S-CCD-TOPT configuration exhibits higher MNA despite having the same RNA mass and inertia, which suggests that the larger platform may experiences higher wave induced excitation, thus leading to a higher transmission of dynamic loads to the tower top. In conclusion, as shown in Fig. 5(c), the adoption of the lightweight generator in combination with tower mass optimization and controller co-design leads to a lower tower-base bending moment DEL than that obtained through the same optimization process with the conventional RNA. A drawback of this solution is the increase in nacelle acceleration, which remains evident under both metocean conditions considered. Figure 6 presents the results for the controller natural frequency (Fig. 6(c)) and damping ratio (Fig. 6(d)), together with the resulting pitch proportional gains (Fig. 6(a)) and integral gains (Fig. 6(b)) for the four optimized configurations. The initial values are set to 0.2 Hz for the natural frequency and to 1 for the damping ratio, as indicated by the red dashed lines. The controller tends to be less reactive at wind speeds lower than 17 m/s in most configurations, with the exception of the B-CCD-TOPT configuration, which exhibits higher values of the natural frequency at 17 m/s and at 23 m/s. For both CCD-TOPT-LWG configurations, the controller natural frequency at 23 m/s is higher than the initial value, leading to a reduction in the rotor response time. The damping ratio increases in the majority of the cases indicating that reducing oscillations during the transient response is prioritized by the optimizer.

Figure 6. Proportional and integral gains of the pitch controller (a,b) for the final optimized design and the tuning controller parameters natural frequency (c) and damping (d). Red dashed line in (c) and (d) is the starting point value for the IEA 15MW RWT.

Figure 7. Ratio of maximum values of the mean maxima within each wind-speed bin of the main parameters for the four analyzed configurations after CCD optimization process. Results are normalized by the reference turbine RWT (a) and by the TOPT CDD optimized configuration (b). All channels are evaluated in DLC 1.1.

The effectiveness of the CCD approach is further reflected in the maximum structural loads and displacement responses. As shown in Fig. 7(a), the final design achieves lower normalized response levels compared to the baseline. The fore–aft nacelle acceleration in the CCD-B-TOPT-

LWG case is substantially reduced while the maximum platform pitch increases in the optimized cases for both Barra configurations. Additional insights can be gained by comparing the TOPT-LWG and TOPT configurations. As observed in Fig. 7(b), the difference in nacelle acceleration is reduced if we consider Figure 4 while platform pitch is increased. Overall, the figure shows the outcome of performing the shown optimization process to two systems derived from the same benchmark turbine, one equipped with a lightweight generator and the other with the conventional generator. To ensure a fair comparison, the final CCD-TOPT-LWG configurations are compared with the corresponding CCD-TOPT configurations (Fig. 7(b)) to isolate the effect of the lightweight generator under the same design procedure. The comparison with the reference RWT configuration shown in Fig. 7(a) remains of interest, as it highlights the extent to which the redesigned and re-optimized turbines differ from the original benchmark.

4. Conclusions

This study explores the potential system-level advantages of integrating a novel lightweight generator design into the IEA 15 MW RWT. The potential benefits and drawbacks of introducing this lightweight generator are investigated under two different metocean conditions. Tower optimizations are performed using the reference and lightweight generators in both investigated metocean conditions. The controller and floating substructure are then co-designed with the objective of minimizing fatigue loads. Results show that a significant mass reduction in the tower is achievable when adopting the lightweight generator concept. By comparing tower designs obtained through the same optimization framework, one with the baseline generator (TOPT) and the other the lightweight generator (TOPT-LWG), it is observed that the use of the lightweight generator allows for a tower mass reduction of up to -16% respect to the TOPT designs. No substantial differences are observed between designs optimized for different metocean conditions as buckling and stress are not active constraints. This indicates that the lower limit imposed on the tower natural frequency is design driving in this case, and the lower generator weight allows this constraint to be relaxed thereby allowing for the observed decreases in tower mass. In the tower-optimized systems, although the mean values of the main structural loads and displacements are lower if compared to those of the IEA 15MW RWT under the same metocean conditions, the maximum values of some parameters such as nacelle acceleration and tower deflection recorded in DLC 1.1 are higher. This behaviour highlights the need for a coupled adaptation of both the floating semisubmersible platform and the main controller parameters to optimize the entire system through a holistic approach that accounts for the modified dynamic properties. Through this coupled optimization process, the tower-base bending moment DEL is reduced. Although the optimization effectively lowers DEL, tower top displacement and nacelle acceleration are still higher if compared to the reference turbine. It should be noted that these preliminary tower designs do not include fatigue load constraints, and no fatigue analysis has been conducted in this study. A comprehensive assessment of the tower design's feasibility requires evaluating fatigue through extensive load analysis, covering a wide range of wind speeds, wind-wave misalignments, significant wave heights, and wave peak periods under normal sea states. In conclusion, while this technology offers significant advantages in terms of mass reduction, both in the tower and generator, with important implications for FOWTs capital expenditure, it also introduces challenges related to maximum nacelle acceleration and displacements, which require further attention.

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